

OPEN PROBLEMS AND CONJECTURES ON THE

FACTOR /RECIPROCAL PARTITION THEORY:

(Amarnath Murthy ,S.E. (E &T), Well Logging Services,Oil And Natural Gas Corporation Ltd. ,Sabarmati, Ahmedbad, India- 380005.)

(1.1) To derive a formula for SFPs of given length m of $p^a q^a$ for any value of a .

(1.2) To derive a formula for SFPs of

$$N = p_1^2 p_2^2 p_3^2 \dots p_r^2$$

(1.3) To derive a formula for SFPs of given length m of

$$N = p_1^\alpha p_2^\alpha p_3^\alpha \dots p_r^\alpha$$

(1.4) To derive a reduction formula for $p^a q^a$ as a linear combination of $p^{a-r} q^{a-r}$ for $r=0$ to $a-1$.

Similar reduction formulae for (1.2) and (1.3) also.

(1.5) In general , in how many ways a number can be expressed as the product of its divisors?

(1.6). Every positive integer can be expressed as the sum of the reciprocal of a finite number of distinct natural numbers. (in infinitely many ways.).

Let us define a function $R_m(n)$ as the minimum number of natural numbers required for such an expression.

(1.7). Every natural number can be expressed as the sum of the reciprocals of a set of natural numbers which are in Arithmetic Progression.

(1.8). Let

$$\sum 1/r \leq n \leq \sum 1/(r+1)$$

where $\sum 1/r$ stands for the sum of the reciprocals of first r natural numbers and let $S_1 = \sum 1/r$

let $S_2 = S_1 + 1/(r+k_1)$ such that $S_2 + 1/(r+k_1+1) > n \geq S_2$

let $S_3 = S_2 + 1/(r+k_2)$ such that $S_3 + 1/(r+k_2+1) > n \geq S_3$

and so on , then there exists a finite m such that

$$S_{m+1} + 1/(r+k_m) = n$$

Remarks : The veracity of conjecture (1.6) is deducible from conjecture (1.8) .

(1.9). (a) There are infinitely many disjoint sets of natural numbers sum of whose reciprocals is unity.

(b) Among the sets mentioned in (a) , there are sets which can be organised in an order such that the largest element of any set is smaller than the smallest element of the next set.

DEFINITION: We can define **Smarandache Factor Partition**

Sequence as follows : $T_n =$ factor partition of $n = F'(n)$

$$T_1 = 1 \cdot T_2 = 3 \cdot T_{12} = 4 \text{ etc.}$$

SFPS is given by

1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 3, 2, 2, 1, 4, 1, 2, 2, 5, 1, 4, 1, 4, 2, 2, 1, 7, 2,

DEFINITION: Let S be the smallest number such that $F'(S) = n$.

We define S a **Vedam Number** and the sequence formed

by Vedam numbers as the **Smarandache Vedam Sequence**.

Smarandache Vedam Sequence is given as follows: $T_n = F'(S)$

1, 4, 8, 12, 16, -?- , 24 ,

Note: There exist no number whose factor partition is equal to 6.

hence a question mark at the sixth slot. We define such numbers

as **Dull numbers**. The readers can explore the distribution

(frequency) and other properties of dull numbers.

DEFINITION: A number n is said to be a **Balu number** if it

satisfies the relation $d(n) = F'(n) = r$, and is the smallest such

number .

1, 16, 36 are all Balu numbers.

$d(1) = F'(1) = 1$ $d(16) = F'(16) = 5$, $d(36) = F'(36) = 9$.

Each Balu number ≥ 16 , generates a **Balu Class** $C_B(n)$ of

numbers having the same canonical form satisfying the equation

$d(m) = F'(m)$. e.g. $C_B(16) = \{ x \mid x = p^4, p \text{ is a prime.} \} = \{ 16, 81,$

$256, \dots \}$. Similarly $C_B(36) = \{ x \mid x = p^2q^2, p \text{ and } q \text{ are primes.} \}$

Conjecture

(1.10): There are only finite number of Balu Classes.

In case Conjecture (1.10) is true , to find out the largest **Balu number**.

REFERENCES

- [1] George E. Andrews, "Number Theory" , Dover Publications Inc. NewYork.
- [2] 'Smarandache Notion Journal' Vol. 10 ,No. 1-2-3, Spring 1999. Number Theory Association of the UNIVERSITY OF CRAIOVA .
- [3] V.Krishnamurthy, "COMBINATORICS Theory and Applications" , East West Press Private Ltd. ,1985.
- [4] "Amarnath Murthy" , 'Generalization Of Partition Function, Introducing 'Smarandache Factor Partition', SNJ, Vol. 11, No. 1-2-3, 2000.
- [5] "Amarnath Murthy" , 'A General Result On The "Smarandache Star Function" , SNJ, Vol. 11, No. 1-2-3, 2000.
- [6] "Amarnath Murthy" , 'More Results And Applications Of The Generalized Smarandache Star Function' SNJ, Vol. 11, No. 1-2-3, 2000.
- [7] "Amarnath Murthy" , 'Length / Extent of Smarandache Factor Partitions. , SNJ, Vol. 11, No. 1-2-3, 2000.
- [8] " The Florentine Smarandache " Special Collection, Archives of American Mathematics, Centre for American History, University of Texax at Austin, USA.